

The Protection of Patient's Sexual Autonomy in Medical Practice and the Concept of Consent in Criminal Law

—A Comparative Legal Study between Japan and Italy, Based on the “Breast Surgeon Case” and the 2023 Reform of the Penal Code—

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1. Introduction

Medical practice inherently involves invasive procedures on a patient's body, the legitimacy of which is founded upon the patient's consent.² However, when such an invasion deviates from its therapeutic purpose and infringes upon the patient's right to sexual self-determination, how should criminal law intervene? This question represents one of the most delicate and challenging issues in medical criminal law. This paper, taking the highly publicized “Breast Surgeon Case” in Japan as its starting point,³ examines the criminal law protection of patient's sexual autonomy in the medical setting. It does so within the new legal context of the “Crime of Non-Consensual Sexual Obscenity” established by the 2023 reform of the Penal Code, through a comparative analysis with Italian law.

The Japanese Breast Surgeon Case involved the question of whether the crime of quasi-forcible sexual obscenity was established against a patient in a state of post-operative delirium. The credibility of the patient's testimony and the evalu -

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² Even for therapeutic purposes, an act that invades the body without the patient's consent could, in principle, fall under the constituent elements of the crime of causing injury (Article 204 of the Penal Code). The victim's consent plays a crucial role in negating its illegality. See Yumi Tomiyama, “Patient's Consent as a Justification Requirement and Informed Consent (1),” *Hokkaido Law Review*, Vol. 72, No. 4 (2021), p. 21.

ation of scientific evidence were contested up to the Supreme Court.⁴ This case exposed the limitations of the former Penal Code in addressing sexual assault in the uniquely vulnerable situation of a medical setting, where a patient is in a state of diminished consciousness, under the requirement of “a state of unconsciousness or inability to resist.” In response, the 2023 Penal Code reform adopted an approach that enumerates specific situations in which it is difficult for a person to form, express, or fulfill an intention not to consent, in order to clarify the scope of criminalization.⁵ It is an urgent task to examine how this reform will affect the resolution of cases like the one in question.

On the other hand, Italy, the country of comparison, has a history of a very high number of criminal prosecutions for medical malpractice, where “defensive medicine” has become a serious social problem.⁶ To address this issue, Italy has undergone reforms to limit the criminal liability of physicians who adhere to guidelines, through legislation such as the “Balduzzi Law” of 2012 and the “Gelli-Bianco Law” of 2017.⁷ Concurrently, Italian medical law has a tradition of emphasizing patient consent (*consenso informato*), and the crime of sexual violence (*violenza sessuale*), unlike the Japanese legal system, has been structured from the outset with the “lack of consent” as its core requirement.⁸

By comparatively analyzing the legal systems of these two countries with such contrasting backgrounds, this paper aims to answer the following research question: In the course of medical practice, particularly in situations where a patient is in a state of diminished consciousness, how do Japan’s newly established “Crime of Non-Consensual Sexual Obscenity” and Italy’s “Crime of Sexual Violence” evaluate the lack of consent in criminal law and construct the criminal liability of

³ A case in which a breast surgeon was prosecuted for the crime of quasi-forcible sexual obscenity for allegedly licking the breast of a female patient after breast cancer surgery in a hospital in Adachi-ku, Tokyo, in 2016. The first instance, the Tokyo District Court, sentenced him to two years of imprisonment. The appellate court, the Tokyo High Court, reversed the decision and acquitted him. The Supreme Court then quashed the acquittal and remanded the case, and the second appellate court acquitted him again, which became final. For details, see Shinichi Oshima, “The Basis for the Supreme Court’s Decision in the Breast Surgeon Case and Its Future Course,” *Nikkei Medical* (March 16, 2022).

⁴ Supreme Court of Japan, Third Petty Bench, Judgment of July 13, 2021 (2020 (A) No. 1029).

⁵ Act for Partial Amendment of the Penal Code and the Code of Criminal Procedure (Act No. 66 of 2023). See Ministry of Justice, “Q&A on the Legal Reform Related to Sex Crimes.”

⁶ Traina, F. “Medical Malpractice: The Experience in Italy,” *Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research*, 467(2), 434–442 (2008).

⁷ Law 8 March 2017, No. 24 (Gelli-Bianco Law); Decree Law 13 September 2012, No. 158 (Balduzzi Law).

⁸ Italian Penal Code, Article 609-bis (*Violenza Sessuale*).

physicians? Furthermore, what implications do the differences in their theoretical construction and procedural guarantees have for medical practice and the protection of patient rights in both countries?

This paper will first analyze the Breast Surgeon Case and the 2023 Penal Code reform in Japan (Chapter 2), then provide an overview of the Italian medical criminal law system, particularly the structure of physician's criminal liability and the crime of sexual violence (Chapter 3). It will then conduct a comparative analysis of the legal systems of both countries, specifically addressing the shared challenges concerning the principle of legality and legal certainty (Chapter 4), and finally, the conclusion will present the criminal law challenges and future prospects for the protection of patient's sexual autonomy in the medical setting.

2. Medical-Related Sex Crimes in Japan and the 2023 Penal Code Reform

2.1. The Scope of the Breast Surgeon Case and the Limits of the “Inability to Resist” Requirement

The Breast Surgeon Case symbolized the difficulty in interpreting the constituent requirement of “taking advantage of a person's state of unconsciousness or inability to resist” under the former crime of quasi-forcible sexual obscenity (former Article 178, paragraph 1 of the Penal Code). The main point of contention in this case was whether Patient A, who was allegedly in a state of delirium after general anesthesia, was in a state of “inability to resist” at the time of the sexual act, and whether the defendant physician was aware of and took advantage of that state.

The Tokyo District Court, in the first instance, found the core part of A's testimony credible, assessed the impact of delirium as limited, and rendered a guilty verdict. In contrast, the Tokyo High Court, in the appellate instance, reversed the decision and acquitted the defendant, stating that the possibility that A had experienced sexual hallucinations due to post-operative delirium could not be ruled out, and that the detection of a third party's DNA, different from the defendant's, on A's clothing raised reasonable doubt about the credibility of her testimony.⁹

⁹ Tokyo High Court, Judgment of February 20, 2019 (2018 (U) No. 1346).

However, the Supreme Court quashed the High Court's decision and remanded the case, stating that the High Court's judgment was "unreasonable and contrary to experience and logic." The Supreme Court pointed out that (1) A's testimony was specific, detailed, realistic, and internally consistent; (2) it was a leap of logic to infer that A had experienced sexual hallucinations solely from the general symptoms of delirium; and (3) the circumstances under which the third party's DNA was attached were unknown and did not immediately affect the credibility of A's testimony.¹⁰ This judgment can be evaluated as a reaffirmation of the basic principle of criminal trials that while the credibility of a victim's testimony should be carefully evaluated, its probative value should not be easily diminished.

Ultimately, in the remanded appellate trial, based on expert opinions newly submitted by the defense, the court again acquitted the defendant, concluding that it had not been "proven beyond a reasonable doubt" that the possibility of sexual hallucinations due to delirium was non-existent. This verdict became final.

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This series of trial proceedings shows that it is extremely difficult to objectively prove the requirement of "inability to resist," as it requires an evaluation of the victim's internal state. Particularly in cases involving disturbances of consciousness such as delirium, it is not easy, either medically or legally, to determine whether the person's words and actions are based on fact or on pathological hallucinations. As a result, the fact-finding of judges fluctuated significantly, which carried the risk of undermining the stability of punishment.

2.2. The 2023 Penal Code Reform and the Establishment of the "Crime of Non-Consensual Sexual Obscenity"

Against the backdrop of such challenges in the old law, the 2023 Penal Code reform integrated the crimes of forcible sexual obscenity and quasi-forcible sexual obscenity, and newly established the "Crime of Non-Consensual Sexual Obscenity" (Article 176 of the Penal Code). The core of this reform is the shift in the basis for punishment from specific means and states such as "assault or intimidation" and "a state of unconsciousness or inability to resist" to causing a person to be in

¹⁰ Supreme Court of Japan, Third Petty Bench, Judgment of July 13, 2021 (2020 (A) No. 1029).

¹¹ Tokyo High Court, Judgment of July 13, 2022 (2021 (U) No. 1143).

“a state in which it is difficult to form, express, or fulfill an intention not to consent” (hereinafter “a state of difficulty in consenting”), or taking advantage of a person being in such a state.¹²

Furthermore, the law enumerates the following eight types of acts and circumstances that can cause this “state of difficulty in consenting”:

1. Assault or intimidation
2. Physical or mental disability
3. The influence of alcohol or drugs
4. Sleep or other states of unclear consciousness
5. Lack of time
6. Fear or astonishment
7. Psychological reaction to abuse
8. The influence of one’s position in an economic or social relationship

With this reform, cases like the Breast Surgeon Case will primarily focus on whether the situation falls under item 4, “sleep or other states of unclear consciousness.” Since a state of delirium after anesthesia is considered a typical example of “a state of unclear consciousness,” the difficulty in interpreting the constituent requirements is expected to be significantly reduced. The prosecutor no longer needs to insist on proving the normative requirement of “inability to resist,” but only needs to prove that the victim was in “a state of unclear consciousness” and that the defendant took advantage of that state to commit an obscene act.

This reform is a major step forward in clarifying the scope of punishment and strengthening the protection of victims’ right to sexual self-determination. However, challenges remain. First, the eight types are merely examples, and there is the question of whether a situation can be evaluated as “a state of difficulty in consenting” even if it does not fall under any of them, and what the criteria for judgment would be in such cases. Second, even if it becomes easier to establish that the constituent requirements are met, the difficulty of fact-finding, such as the credibility of the victim’s testimony and the evaluation of scientific evidence,

¹² See Criminal Affairs Bureau, Ministry of Justice, “Outline of the 2023 Partial Amendment of the Penal Code, etc.”

as shown in the Breast Surgeon Case, will not be resolved. Rather, as the hurdle for the constituent requirements has been lowered, even more careful and appropriate fact-finding will be required.

3. Medical Criminal Law and Sexual Self-Determination in Italy

3.1. The Evolution of Legal Reforms Concerning Physician's Criminal Liability

For many years, Italian medical criminal law has faced the serious problem of a high number of criminal prosecutions against physicians. The high risk of being prosecuted for crimes such as causing personal injury through negligence (*lesioni personali colpose*) even for minor errors has led to the spread of “defensive medicine (*medicina difensiva*),” in which physicians perform excessive tests and prescribe excessive medication for self-protection, or conversely, avoid high-risk treatments, leading to a decline in the quality of medical care and an increase in medical costs.¹³

To overcome this situation, the Italian Parliament has carried out two important legal reforms.

The first reform was the “Balduzzi Law (*Legge Balduzzi*)” of 2012. This law stipulated that as long as a physician complies with “guidelines and good clinical practices accredited by the scientific community (*linee guida e buone pratiche accreditate dalla comunità scientifica*),” they are exempt from criminal liability for slight negligence (*colpa lieve*).¹⁴ This was a groundbreaking attempt to respect the discretion of physicians and to ensure the subsidiarity of criminal punishment, but it left many interpretative problems, such as the fact that liability could still be pursued in cases of gross negligence (*colpa grave*), and the definition and effect of “guidelines” were unclear.¹⁵

¹³ Zerbo, S., Malta, G., & Argo, A. (2020). Guidelines and Current Assessment of Health Care Responsibility in Italy. *Risk Management and Healthcare Policy*, 13, 183–189.

¹⁴ Decree Law 13 September 2012, No. 158, art. 3.

¹⁵ Franciosi, L. M. (2018). The New Italian Regime for Healthcare Liability and the Role of Clinical Practice Guidelines: A Dialogue among Legal Formants. *Journal of Civil Law Studies*, 11.

Therefore, as a more comprehensive reform, the “Gelli-Bianco Law (Legge Gelli-Bianco)” was enacted in 2017. This law positions the safety of care (sicurezza delle cure) as part of the fundamental right to health and aims for a systematic institutional reform, such as obligating medical institutions to establish risk management systems.¹⁶

Regarding criminal liability, it newly established Article 590-sexies of the Penal Code and redefined the liability of healthcare professionals as follows:

If a medical act is performed in compliance with the relevant guidelines (or, in their absence, good clinical practices), and the negligence is due to a lack of skill (imperizia), it is not punishable. However, this does not apply if the lack of skill is evaluated as gross negligence.

This provision, in principle, made negligence due to a slight lack of skill (imperizia) unpunishable, as long as the physician complies with the guidelines. On the other hand, negligence due to a breach of the duty of care (negligenza) or recklessness (imprudenza) remained punishable even if it was slight negligence. This reform is an attempt to make the scope of physicians’ criminal liability more limited and predictable, and it is expected to curb defensive medicine, but its effects are still being debated.¹⁷

3.2. The Crime of Sexual Violence (Violenza Sessuale) and the Requirement of “Consent”

The crime of sexual violence (art. 609-bis c.p.) in the Italian Penal Code was reorganized from a crime against public morals to a crime against the person by the 1996 legal reform, and its constituent requirements were also significantly changed. The current law punishes “anyone who, by violence, threat, or abuse of authority (abuso di autorità), forces another to perform or undergo sexual acts.”

A crucial feature in comparison with Japanese law is that the “lack of consent” is clearly positioned at the core of the crime’s establishment. Violence, threats, and abuse of authority are understood as means to deprive the victim of the free -

¹⁶ Law 8 March 2017, No. 24. Commonly known as the “Gelli-Bianco Law.”

¹⁷ Albano, G. D., et al. (2022). The Impact on Healthcare Workers of Italian Law n. 24/2017 ‘Gelli-Bianco’ on Patient Safety and Medical Liability: A National Survey. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(14), 8448.

dom to form and express consent. Therefore, even without explicit violence or threats, if a sexual act is performed without the patient's valid consent by taking advantage of the asymmetrical relationship between a physician and a patient, it can be considered an "abuse of authority" and this crime can be established.

The Italian Supreme Court (Court of Cassation) has accumulated important precedents regarding the application of this crime in the medical setting. For example, in one judgment, regarding an act in which a gynecologist touched a patient's sexual parts deviating from the purpose of the examination, the court ruled that "the patient had consented to the therapeutic act, but that did not mean consent to the sexual act," and recognized the physician's abuse of authority.¹⁸ In another case, an act that took advantage of a patient's drowsy state due to anesthesia was also affirmed as an application of this crime, as it took advantage of the victim's lack of capacity to consent.¹⁹

As is clear from these precedents, in Italian law, (1) general consent to a medical act and (2) consent to an individual sexual act are clearly distinguished. And if the latter consent is lacking, even if it is performed in the context of treatment, the establishment of the crime of sexual violence cannot be avoided. This "consent-centric" construction provides a strong theoretical basis for respecting the victim's subjective will and protecting the right to sexual self-determination.

4. Comparative Legal Analysis and Discussion

Japan's new "Crime of Non-Consensual Sexual Obscenity" and Italy's "Crime of Sexual Violence" both aim to protect the victim's right to sexual self-determination, but their approaches show marked differences. This chapter compares the legal systems of both countries and considers their theoretical implications and practical challenges, particularly focusing on the shared dilemma regarding the principle of legality.

¹⁸ Cass. pen., Sez. III, n. 18864/2019. This judgment is important in that it emphasizes the physician's duty to respect the patient's right to sexual self-determination.

¹⁹ Maghin, F., et al. (2021). Sexual violence: 10 years of case studies in a hospital in Northern Italy. *Journal of Public Health Research*, 10(4), 2564.

4.1. The Structure of Constituent Requirements: Enumeration of “States” vs. Lack of “Consent”

The most fundamental difference lies in where the core of the crime’s establishment is placed. The following table summarizes this structural difference.

Comparison Item	Japan: Crime of Non-Consensual Sexual Obscenity (Post-Reform)	Italy: Crime of Sexual Violence
Core Concept	State of difficulty in consenting	Lack of consent
Approach	An objective and typological approach that enumerates eight typical “states” in which it is difficult to consent.	A subjective and principled approach that creates a state of “no consent” through means such as violence, threats, or abuse of authority.
Focus of Proof	That the victim was in one of the eight enumerated states, and that the perpetrator took advantage of that state.	That there was no valid consent from the victim, and that this was due to the perpetrator’s coercive act.
Application to the Medical Setting	Mainly related to “sleep or other states of unclear consciousness” (item 4) and “the influence of one’s position in an economic or social relationship” (item 8).	“Abuse of authority (abuso di autorità)” is directly applicable to the physician-patient relationship.

Japan’s 2023 reform chose the path of enumerating objectively recognizable “states” to overcome the ambiguity of the normative requirement of “inability to resist” in the old law. As a result, a state of delirium after anesthesia, as in the Breast Surgeon Case, now clearly falls under the constituent requirement of “a state of unclear consciousness” in item 4, and the clarity and stability of punishment have improved. This is, so to speak, a “typological approach,” an attempt to draw the outline of punishable acts as specifically as possible at the legislative stage.

In contrast, Italian law maintains the more abstract and principled requirement of “lack of consent.” And by citing “abuse of authority” as a means of infringing on that consent, it directly addresses sexual exploitation in inherently asymmetrical power relationships, such as that between a physician and a patient.

This is a “principled approach,” which emphasizes that the judge should substantially determine the presence or absence of “consent” and the manner of its infringement according to the specific circumstances of each case.

4.2. The Distinction Between Informed Consent and Sexual Consent

The particularity of sexual assault in the medical setting lies in the intersection of general consent to a therapeutic act (informed consent) and consent to an individual sexual act. The patient allows the physician to invade their body for the purpose of treatment. The essence of the crime discussed in this paper is the abuse of this relationship of trust to engage in sexual acts that deviate from the therapeutic purpose.

In Italian law, these two types of consent are clearly distinguished. Consent to treatment does not include consent to sexual acts. Therefore, it is considered that a physician has a duty to obtain separate, clear consent for acts that may touch on the patient’s right to sexual self-determination, even if they are necessary for treatment.²⁰ This idea is extremely important in thoroughly protecting patient rights.

On the other hand, Japan’s 2023 revised law does not directly regulate this point. However, it is noteworthy that item 8 lists “causing a person to worry about disadvantages they may suffer due to their position in an economic or social relationship, or taking advantage of their worrying about it” as one type of state of difficulty in consenting. The physician-patient relationship is precisely a situation where this “influence of one’s position in a social relationship” is prominent. Engaging in sexual acts by taking advantage of a patient’s worries, such as “my treatment might be discontinued” or “I might be disadvantaged in future consultations,” could fall under the application of this item. As a result, it is expected that Japanese law can also indirectly fulfill a function similar to the “abuse of authority” in Italian law.

²⁰ Di Paolo, M., et al. (2019). A Review and Analysis of New Italian Law 219/2017: ‘Provisions for Informed Consent and Advance Directives’. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 20:17.

4.3. The Shared Dilemma: The Principle of Legality and the Problem of Predictability

While the 2023 reform in Japan aimed to clarify the scope of punishment, it raises serious concerns from the perspective of the principle of legality, particularly the principle of clarity (*lex certa*). The principle of legality, enshrined in Article 31 of the Japanese Constitution and Article 38, paragraph 1 of the Penal Code, requires that criminal provisions be sufficiently clear and specific to enable citizens to predict which acts are punishable.²¹

The eight enumerated “states of difficulty in consenting” in the reformed Article 176 are intended to provide concrete guidance. However, several of these categories remain inherently vague and subject to broad interpretation. For instance, item 4, “sleep or other states of unclear consciousness,” does not specify the degree of impairment required. In the medical context, patients may experience varying levels of consciousness due to sedation, anesthesia, or post-operative delirium. At what point does a patient’s diminished but not absent consciousness constitute a “state of unclear consciousness” sufficient to establish criminal liability? The law provides no clear threshold. Furthermore, the eight enumerated states are explicitly non-exhaustive (situations “such as” those listed), leaving open the possibility that courts may find other, unenumerated circumstances to constitute “states of difficulty in consenting.”

It is crucial to note that this tension with the principle of legality is not unique to Japan’s typological approach; it is equally, if not more, pronounced in Italy’s principled approach. Article 25, paragraph 2 of the Italian Constitution guarantees the principle of legality (*principio di legalità*), and its sub-principle, the principle of determinateness (*principio di tassatività / determinatezza*), strictly requires clarity in criminal statutes.²² However, Article 609-bis of the Italian Penal Code has long been criticized by legal scholars for its “vagueness of description.”²³

Specifically, the Italian law lacks a statutory definition of “sexual acts (*atti sessuali*),” leaving the boundary between legitimate medical examination and sexual assault entirely to judicial interpretation.²⁴ Moreover, the concept of “abuse of

²¹ Takahashi, N. (2015). *The Principle of Legality in Japanese Criminal Law*. *Waseda Law Review*, 90(3).

²² Sartori, D. (2014). *The lex certa principle: From the Italian Constitution to the European Convention on Human Rights*. Doctoral dissertation, University of Trento.

authority (abuso di autorità)” is highly indeterminate regarding the degree of power asymmetry required for its application.²⁵ Consequently, the substantive definition of the crime has been heavily supplemented by the case law of the Court of Cassation, creating a tension with the principle that crimes must be defined by parliamentary law (riserva di legge).

This shared dilemma—the difficulty of achieving both comprehensive protection of sexual autonomy and strict adherence to the principle of legality—has recently manifested in intense political debate in Italy. During the 2025-2026 legislative discussions to further reform the sexual violence law, a proposal to explicitly define rape based on the “absence of consent” faced strong opposition from political factions arguing that the concept of consent “leaves too much room for individual interpretation” and lacks legal certainty.²⁶ This led to a regressive amendment requiring proof of “explicit refusal,” highlighting how the demand for legal clarity can sometimes conflict with the realities of sexual victimization.²⁷

In conclusion, both Japan’s typological approach (which is rigid but aspires to clarity) and Italy’s principled approach (which is flexible but inherently ambiguous) face the same fundamental aporia: neither can perfectly satisfy the demands of the principle of legality (*lex certa*) in the complex and nuanced context of medical practice.

4.4. Comparative Analysis with Similar Italian Case Law

A recent decision by the Italian Supreme Court offers significant insights for the debate in Japan regarding the determination of sexual violence in a medical context. In particular, the 2019 gynecologist case (Cass. pen., Sez. III, n. 18864/2019) analyzed in this paper is highly suggestive in comparison to the Japanese Breast Surgeon Case.

²³ Parlato, L., & Palmisano, M. (2023). Italian Criminal Justice and Sexual Offenses. In *European Perspectives on Attrition in Sexual Offenses* (p. 141).

²⁵ Macrì, F. (2016). La violenza sessuale (art. 609-bis CP) nella giurisprudenza della Suprema Corte del 2015. *Diritto penale contemporaneo*.

²⁶ Human Rights Watch. (2026, January 27). The Absence of No is Not Yes: Italy’s Flawed Sexual Violence Bill. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2026/01/27/the-absence-of-no-is-not-yes-italys-flawed-sexual-violence-bill>

²⁷ Ibid.

In that ruling, the Supreme Court overturned the acquittal of a gynecologist who had sexually stimulated a patient without her consent during an examination. The Court emphasized the following points in its reasoning:

1. **Strict Requirement for Explicit Consent:** It ruled that even in the context of medical treatment, explicit and fully informed consent is indispensable for any act involving the sexual sphere, and that the mere act of entering the examination room cannot be deemed as “implied consent.” This demonstrates a stance that maximally respects the patient’s right to self-determination.
2. **Irrelevance of Sexual Intent:** It clearly stated that the physician’s subjective sexual arousal or intent for satisfaction is not necessary for the crime to be established. The objective fact that an act of a sexual nature was performed without the patient’s valid consent is sufficient. This provides a clear answer to the debate over the necessity of “sexual intent,” which was a point of contention in the Japanese Breast Surgeon Case.
3. **Emphasis on the Patient’s Psychological State:** The Court actively evaluated the patient’s state of being “surprised and unable to react immediately” as a crucial element supporting the absence of consent. This shows that the judiciary recognizes the reality that in situations of asymmetrical power dynamics, victims may not always be able to show clear refusal.

The legal principles from this Italian case are in line with the direction aimed for by Japan’s 2023 legal reform, and serve as an important comparative reference, especially in interpreting cases involving “a state of unclear consciousness” or “taking advantage of influence.” The history of the Italian judiciary deepening the protection of sexual self-determination through case law, ahead of legislation, is suggestive for the future interpretation and application of the “crime of non-consensual sexual indecency” in Japan.

4.5. Procedural Guarantees and the Challenges of Fact-Finding

No matter how refined the structure of the constituent requirements may be, strict proof is required to ultimately hold someone criminally liable. As the Breast Surgeon Case showed, it is extremely difficult to prove an act that takes place in the closed room of a medical setting, and the evaluation of the credibility of the victim’s testimony determines the outcome of the trial.

Japan's legal reform has contributed to the clarification of the constituent requirements, but it does not directly resolve the difficulty of fact-finding. Rather, it has been pointed out that the perception that the scope of punishment has been expanded may cause physicians to become overly cautious and promote defensive medicine.²⁸ The possibility that the problem of defensive medicine, which Italy has long suffered from, may appear in Japan in a different form cannot be denied.

In this regard, the fact that Italy's Gelli-Bianco Law is promoting the strengthening of risk management systems in medical institutions and the development of dispute resolution mechanisms in parallel with the limitation of criminal liability is suggestive.²⁹ Before resorting to the last resort of criminal punishment, a multi-layered institutional design to prevent medical errors and ethical violations and to provide relief to victims is indispensable. The reform of criminal law should be positioned as part of such a comprehensive medical safety system.

5. Conclusion

This paper has considered the issue of protecting patient's right to sexual self-termination in the medical setting through a comparative analysis with Italian law, based on the Breast Surgeon Case in Japan and the 2023 Penal Code reform.

Japan's 2023 reform has shown great progress in that it has overcome the ambiguous requirement of "inability to resist" and has increased the clarity and stability of punishment by specifically enumerating the states in which it is difficult to consent. In particular, sexual assault against a patient in a state of diminished consciousness, as in the Breast Surgeon Case, is now clearly included in the constituent requirements of the newly established Crime of Non-Consensual Sexual Obscenity, which can be said to be a step forward from the perspective of victim protection.

However, Japan's "typological approach" leaves challenges in responding to various types of victimization other than the enumerated states and in dealing with problems such as the abuse of the power relationship between physicians and patients. In contrast, the "principled approach" of Italian law, which places

²⁸ Leflar, R. B., & Iwata, M. (2005). Medical Error as Reportable Event, as Tort, as Crime: A Transpacific Comparison. *Widener Law Review*, 12, 189.

²⁹ Bargelli, E., & Bacciardi, E. (2021). Medical Liability in Italy after the 'Gelli-Bianco' Reform (Law 8 March 2017, No. 24). *Gdańskie Studia Prawnicze*.

the “lack of consent” at its core and responds to the particularity of the physician-patient relationship with the concept of “abuse of authority,” more directly captures the essence of the crime, which is the protection of the right to sexual self-determination.

Crucially, our comparative analysis reveals that both approaches struggle with the demands of the principle of legality (*lex certa*). While Japan’s enumerated states retain inherent ambiguities (e.g., the threshold for “unclear consciousness”), Italy’s reliance on abstract concepts like “sexual acts” and “abuse of authority” has drawn persistent criticism for violating the principle of determinateness (*principio di tassatività*), leading to recent political pushback against consent-based definitions. This shared dilemma underscores that the complex problem of sexual assault in the medical setting cannot be perfectly solved by the constituent requirements of criminal law alone.

As the Italian experience shows, in order to effectively protect patient rights without causing physicians to shy away from legitimate medical practice, a comprehensive approach that includes not only the refinement of criminal liability but also governance in medical institutions, ethics education, and the establishment of a prompt victim relief system is indispensable. It is our future task to make Japan’s 2023 Penal Code reform a milestone in fostering such a comprehensive medical safety culture.

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